

BUCKLING AND POST-BUCKLING OF LAMINATED NON-CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

Izhak Sheinman and Marina Firer
Faculty of Civil Engineering
Technion – Israel Institute of Technology

ABSTRACT

An analytical–numerical procedure is applied to investigate the buckling and post–buckling behavior of laminated cylindrical shells with non–circular cross–section of arbitrary closed shape. The buckling and post–buckling analysis are based on Donnell's nonlinear kinematic relations. The curvature, which is a function of the circumferential coordinate, is expanded in Fourier series. The numerical procedure is based on separation of variables and their expansion into Fourier series. Through the Galerkin procedure, the field and boundary equations, written in terms of the transverse displacement and Airy stress function, are reduced to a system of ordinary differential equations, which are solved by finite difference scheme. The configuration aspect is investigated parametrically. Unlike the circular cylindrical shells, coupling of the wave number in the circumferential direction is significantly high.

Keywords: Buckling, post–buckling, oval cylindrical shells, composite materials, non–linear

INTRODUCTION

Shells configuration with a non–circular cross–section are already widely used in industrial applications. their buckling and post–buckling behavior is a vital safety consideration. Thus, improvement in the accuracy of predicting this behavior are essential for reliable design.

The nonlinear behavior of shell like structures is generally characterized by a limit point rather than by a bifurcation point (buckling analysis); still, bifurcation analysis, beside the limit point, can be used as a guideline and a basic procedure for examining the imperfection sensitivity. For the limit point, the entire nonlinear behavior must be known.

Extensive research on buckling and postbuckling behavior of laminated circular cylindrical shells is reported in the literature (see Ref [1]), while very few deal with non–circular cylindrical shells. A review of the earliest works can be found in Refs [2] and [3]. These include the papers of Kempner and Chen (Ref [4] and [5]), and later those of Hutchinson [6], Feinstein et al. ([7] and [8]), and Chen and Kempner [9]).

Buckling of laminated composite non–circular cylindrical shells was analyzed by Soldatos and Tzivanidis ([10]) and more recently by Sun ([11]). All these papers deal with specific non–circular shapes, namely elliptic and oval ones, whose relative imperfection sensitivity was studied by Hutchinson ([6]).

The object of the present work is a refined buckling and post-buckling analysis for laminated cylindrical shells with a non-circular cross-section of arbitrary closed shape. The closed shape may be treated as a periodic function and accordingly expanded in Fourier series in terms of the circumferential angle coordinate.

Of the different shell theories (see Refs [2], [12], and [13]) Donnell-type equations were adopted here for the kinematic approach because of its relative simplicity. They are sufficiently accurate, provided both the length of the cylinder and the oval eccentricity parameter are small. For larger values, they can be used only for indication of the behavior. The analysis is based on the classical laminate theory and the equations are written in terms of the normal displacement (W) and the Airy stress function (F). The solution procedure is based on separation of the variables as Fourier series in the circumferential direction and by finite differences in the meridional direction. Since the curvature is written, for convenience, in terms of circumferential angle coordinate (θ) rather than of the circumferential arc-length, the system is transformed to the former. The Galerkin procedure is used to minimize the errors due to the truncated series and to non-compliance the natural boundary conditions. The procedure is illustrated on an isotropic and laminated non-circular cylindrical shell under axial compression. The configuration aspect is examined parametrically in the elliptic and oval cross-section cases.

GEOMETRY OF NON-CIRCULAR CYLINDER

Two non-circular configurations are widely discussed in literature (see for example Refs [3], [5], [6], and [11]). They are

(1) *elliptic*, represented by the equation

$$\left[\frac{\bar{y}}{A} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\bar{z}}{B} \right]^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where \bar{y} and \bar{z} are the major and minor coordinates of the ellipse (see Figure 1), A and B the half-axes in the \bar{y} and \bar{z} directions. The circumferential radius of curvature is given by:

$$R(y) = \frac{A^2}{B} \left\{ 1 + \left[\left(\frac{B}{A} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \left[\frac{\bar{y}(y)}{2} \right]^2 \right\}^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

(2) nonellipsoidal *oval*, whose radius of curvature is given by:

$$R(y) = \frac{R_0}{1 + \xi \frac{\cos(2y/R_0)}{c}} \quad (3)$$

ξ being the eccentricity parameter and R_0 the radius of a circular cylinder with the same circumference.

Analysis for a non-circular cross-section necessitates a general expression for the curvature of any arbitrary configuration. The shape of the cross section can be considered as a periodic function of the circumferential angle (θ) ($R(\theta) = R(\theta+2\pi)$) and can be described in terms of a Fourier series. The present study is confined to a cross section with at least two axes of symmetry, thus:

$$\frac{1}{R(\theta)} = \sum_{k=0}^{NR} \alpha_k \cos(2k\theta) \quad (4)$$

where θ is the angle coordinate (Figure 1) and NR is the number of terms in the truncated series for the curvature. The curvature of elliptic (Equation 2) and oval* (Equation 3)

*It should be noted here that the oval configuration was considered in order to simplify the analysis: it is merely an approximate equivalent expression in R_0 and may deviate significantly from the actual cross-section.

cross-sections can be described exactly by the Fourier series of Equation 4. An example of three configurations with small, medium and large eccentricity is given in Table 1. In this table the fourier coefficients of the elliptic shape are for the same major and minor axes length (A and B). The convergence of the Fourier series is shown in Figure 2 for the medium and large eccentricities.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Let (x,y) be the shell coordinates of the reference surface and z the inward normal coordinate (Figure 1). Application of the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis as basic assumption leaves three dependent variables, U, V and W , respectively. Resorting to the Von Karman nonlinear kinematic approach for a geometrically imperfect $(\bar{W}(x,y))$ shell, the strain-displacement can be written as

$$\{\epsilon\} = \{\bar{\epsilon}\} + z\{\chi\} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}\} = \begin{cases} \bar{\epsilon}_{xx} = U_{,x} + \frac{1}{2}W_{,x} (W_{,x} + 2\bar{W}_{,x}) \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{yy} = V_{,y} + \frac{1}{2}W_{,y} (W_{,y} + 2\bar{W}_{,y}) - \frac{W}{R(\theta)} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{xy} = U_{,y} + V_{,x} + \frac{1}{2}W_{,x} (W_{,y} + 2\bar{W}_{,y}) + \frac{1}{2}W_{,y} (W_{,x} + 2\bar{W}_{,x}) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\{\chi\} = \begin{cases} \chi_{xx} = -W_{,xx} \\ \chi_{yy} = -W_{,yy} \\ \chi_{xy} = -2W_{,xy} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$(\)_{,x}$ and $(\)_{,y}$ denote the derivatives in the meridional (x) and circumferential (y) direction, respectively.

Introduction of the Airy stress function (F) reduces the system to only two dependent variables (W and F). The function is defined by the following relationship:

$$\{N\} = \{F\} + \{\bar{N}\} \quad (8)$$

where $\{N\} = \{N_{xx}, N_{yy}, N_{xy}\}$ is the internal membrane force vector, $\{F\} = \{F_{,yy}, F_{,xx}, -F_{,xy}\}$ the Airy stress vector and $\{\bar{N}\} = \{\bar{N}_{xx}, \bar{N}_{yy}, \bar{N}_{xy}\}$ the external inplane loading applied at the boundaries.

Under the classical laminate theory the strain $\{\bar{\epsilon}\}$ and the bending moment $\{M\} (= \{M_{xx}, M_{yy}, M_{xy}\})$ can be expressed in terms of $\{F\}$, the curvature $\{\chi\}$ and the inplane external loading $\{\bar{N}\}$ as

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}\} = [a]\{F + \bar{N}\} - [b]\{\chi\} \quad (9)$$

$$\{M\} = [b]^T\{F + \bar{N}\} + [d]\{\chi\}$$

where $a = A^{-1}$; $b = A^{-1}B$; $d = D - BA^{-1}B$

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_z Q_{ij}(1 - z^2) dz \quad (10)$$

A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} being, respectively, the membrane, coupling and flexural rigidities and Q_{ij} the laminate transformed reduced stiffnesses.

The governing equations in W and F are derived via the Hu–Washizu mixed formulation for the potential energy (see Sheinman and Reichman [14]).

Equilibrium:

$$L_h(W) + L_q(F) + L(F + \bar{N}, W + \bar{W}) + \frac{(F_{,xx} + \bar{N}_{yy})}{R(\theta)} - q = 0 \quad (11)$$

Compatibility:

$$L_q(W) + L_g(F) + \frac{1}{2}L(W, W, +2\bar{W}) + \frac{W_{,xx}}{R(\theta)} = 0$$

where q is the external applied normal load L and L_p are differential operators defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} L(S, T) &= S_{,xx}T_{,yy} - 2S_{,xy}T_{,xy} + S_{,yy}T_{,xx} \\ L_p(S) &= p_{40}S_{,xxxx} + p_{31}S_{,xxxxy} + p_{22}S_{,xxyy} \\ &\quad + p_{13}S_{,xyyy} + p_{04}S_{,yyyy} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

with $p = h, g$ and q . The coefficients h_{ij} , g_{ij} and q_{ij} , which are expressed in terms of the laminate properties $[a]$, $[b]$ and $[d]$ are given in [15].

The buckling equations are obtained by omitting the imperfection \bar{W} and by employing the following perturbation technique

$$\begin{aligned} W &= W^{(0)} + \lambda W^{(1)} \\ F &= F^{(0)} + \lambda F^{(1)} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

substituting equations (13) into the potential energy yield:

$$\pi = \pi^{(0)} + \lambda \pi^{(1)} + \lambda^2 \pi^{(2)} \quad (14)$$

The prebuckling equations are derived by setting $\delta\pi^{(1)} = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} L_h(W^{(0)}) + L_q(F^{(0)}) + L(F^{(0)} + \bar{N}, W^{(0)}) + \frac{(F_{,xx}^{(0)} + \bar{N}_{yy})}{R(\theta)} - q = 0 \\ L_q(W^{(0)}) + L_g(F^{(0)}) + \frac{1}{2}L(W^{(0)}, W^{(0)}) + \frac{W_{,xx}^{(0)}}{R(\theta)} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

and the buckling equations by setting $\delta\pi^{(2)} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} L_h(W^{(1)}) + L_q(F^{(1)}) + L(F^{(1)}, W^{(0)}) + L(F^{(0)} + \bar{N}, W^{(1)}) + \frac{F_{,xx}^{(1)}}{R(\theta)} = 0 \\ L_q(W^{(1)}) + L_g(F^{(1)}) + L(W^{(0)}, W^{(1)}) + \frac{W_{,xx}^{(1)}}{R(\theta)} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Equations 15a and 16a refer to the equilibrium and 15b and 16b to the compatibility. The boundary conditions, which are derived in the same manner as in Ref [16] fall into three

distinct groups: Simply-supported SS_i ($W = M_{xx} = 0$); clamped CC_i ($W = W_{,x} = 0$) and free FF_i ($Q_x^* = M_{xx} = 0$). The subscript $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ denotes the following inplane conditions: $i = 1$ for $F_{,xy} = F_{,yy} = 0$; $i = 2$ for $F_{,xy} = 0, U = c$; $i = 3$ for $V = F_{,yy} = 0$; and $i = 4$ for $V = 0, U = c$ where c is a constant.

Since the general Fourier expansion of the curvature (Equation 4) is written in terms of the angle θ rather than in that of the circumferential y -coordinate, the system equation (Equations 11, 15, 16 and boundary conditions) must be transformed from the latter to the former. The transformation is effected through the differential operators L and L_p defined in Equation 12 as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{L}(S, T) = & S_{,xx}[r r_{,\theta} T_{,\theta} + r^2 T_{,\theta\theta}] - 2[r S_{,\theta}]_{,x}[r T_{,\theta}]_{,x} \\ & + [r r_{,\theta} S_{,\theta} + r^2 S_{,\theta\theta}] T_{,xx} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{L}_p(S) = & p_{40} S_{,xxxx} + p_{31} [r S_{,\theta}]_{,xxx} + p_{22} [r r_{,\theta} S_{,\theta} + r^2 S_{,\theta\theta}]_{,xx} \\ & + p_{13} [r r^2_{,\theta} S_{,\theta} + r^2 r_{,\theta\theta} S_{,\theta} + 3r^2 r_{,\theta} S_{,\theta\theta} + r^3 S_{,\theta\theta\theta}]_{,x} \\ & + p_{04} [r r^3_{,\theta} S_{,\theta} + 4r^2 r_{,\theta} r_{,\theta\theta} S_{,\theta} + r^3 r_{,\theta\theta\theta} S_{,\theta} + \\ & 7r^2 r^2_{,\theta} S_{,\theta\theta} + 4r^3 r_{,\theta\theta} S_{,\theta\theta} + 6r^3 r_{,\theta} S_{,\theta\theta\theta} + r^4 S_{,\theta\theta\theta\theta}] \end{aligned}$$

where $r = r(\theta) = \frac{1}{R(\theta)}$

SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

The set of partial differential equations is first reduced to one of ordinary differential equations by separation of variables as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W}(x, \theta) &= \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \bar{w}_m(x) g_m(\theta) \\ W(x, \theta) &= \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} w_m(x) g_m(\theta) \\ F(x, \theta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} f_n(x) g_n(\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

NW and NF being the number of retained terms in the truncated series for W and F , respectively, and

$$g_m(\theta) = \begin{cases} \cos(im\theta) & m = 0, 1, \dots, NWF \\ \sin(im\theta) & m = NWF + 1 \dots 2NWF \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$NWF = NW$ for the W -series and $= NF$ for the F -series. i denotes the characteristic circumferential wave number. Recourse to a characteristic wave number makes it possible in some cases to reduce substantially the number of terms in the Fourier series (see ref [17]). For general cases in which all terms are significant, it is necessary to let $i = 1$ and m and n sufficiently large for an accurate representation of W and F . Applying the Galerkin

procedure for minimizing the errors due to the shortcomings of the system equations, the following integrals are eliminated:

$$\oint (\text{Equilibrium equation}) g_w^j(\theta) d\theta = 0$$

$$j = 0, 1, \dots, 2NW$$

$$\oint (\text{Compatibility equation}) g_f^j(\theta) d\theta = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$j = 0, 1, \dots, 2NF$$

where g_w^j and g_f^j are the weighted functions, chosen as $\cos(ij\theta)$ and $\sin(ij\theta)$. With all the above steps implemented we arrive at the following ordinary differential equations:

Equilibrium:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \{h_{40}A_0(m,p) w_{m,xxxx}^{(e)} + h_{31}A_1(m,p) w_{m,xxx}^{(e)} + \\ & [h_{22}A_2(m,p) - \eta \bar{N}_{xx}A_0(m,p)] w_{m,xx}^{(e)} + [h_{13}A_3(m,p) - \eta \cdot 2\bar{N}_{xy}A_1(m,p)] w_{m,x}^{(e)} \\ & + [h_{04}A_4(m,p) - \eta \bar{N}_{yy}A_2(m,p)] w_m^{(e)}\} \\ & + \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{q_{40}A_0(n,p) f_{n,xxxx}^{(e)} + q_{31}A_1(n,p) f_{n,xxx}^{(e)} + [q_{22}A_2(n,p) + B_1(n,p)] f_{n,xx}^{(e)} \\ & + q_{13}A_3(n,p) f_{n,x}^{(e)} + q_{04}A_4(n,p) f_n^{(e)}\} \\ & + \delta_1 \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{AN1(m,n,p) (f_n^{(0)} w_{m,xx}^{(1)} + f_n^{(1)} w_{m,xx}^{(0)}) \\ & + AN1(n,m,p) (f_{n,xx}^{(0)} w_m^{(1)} + f_{n,xx}^{(1)} w_m^{(0)}) \\ & + 2AN2(m,n,p) (f_{n,x}^{(0)} w_{m,x}^{(1)} + f_{n,x}^{(1)} w_{m,x}^{(0)}) \\ & + \delta_2 \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{AN1(m,n,p) (f_n^{(e)} (w_{m,xx}^{(e)} + \bar{w}_{m,xx}) + f_{n,xx}^{(e)} (w_m^{(e)} + \bar{w}_m)) \\ & + 2AN2(m,n,p) (f_{n,x}^{(e)} (w_{m,x}^{(e)} + \bar{w}_{m,x}))\} = (1-\delta_1)2\pi q \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$p = 0, 1, \dots, 2NW$$

Compatibility:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \{q_{40}A_0(m,p) w_{m,xxxx}^{(e)} + q_{31}A_1(m,p) w_{m,xxx}^{(e)} \\ & + [q_{22}A_2(m,p) + B_1(m,p)] w_{m,xx}^{(e)} + q_{13}A_3(m,p) w_{m,x}^{(e)} + q_{04}A_4(m,p) w_m^{(e)}\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{g_{40}A_0(n,p)f_{n,xxxx}^{(e)} + g_{31}A_1(n,p)f_{n,xxxx}^{(e)} + g_{22}A_2(n,p)f_{n,xx}^{(e)} \\
& + g_{13}A_3(n,p)f_{n,x}^{(e)} + g_{04}A_4(n,p)f_n^{(e)}\} \\
& + \delta_1 \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{AN1(m,n,p) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ w_m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w_{n,xx} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w_m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ w_{n,xx} \end{pmatrix} \\
& + AN2(m,n,p) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ w_{m,x} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w_{n,x} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w_{m,x} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ w_{n,x} \end{pmatrix}\} \\
& + \delta_2 \sum_{m=0}^{2NW} \sum_{n=0}^{2NF} \{AN1(m,n,p) (\frac{1}{2}w_n^{(e)}(w_{m,xx}^{(e)} + 2\bar{w}_{m,xx})) \\
& + \frac{1}{2}w_{n,xx}^{(e)}(w_m^{(e)} + \bar{w}_m)) + 2AN2(m,n,p) (\begin{pmatrix} e \\ w_{n,x} \end{pmatrix} (\begin{pmatrix} e \\ w_{m,x} \end{pmatrix} + \bar{w}_{m,x}))\} = 0 \\
& \qquad \qquad \qquad p = 0, 1, \dots, 2NF
\end{aligned}$$

The superscript e and the multipliers δ_1 and δ_2 indicate the state: $e = 0$, $\delta_1 = 0$, $\delta_2 = 1$ for prebuckling state, $\delta_2 = 0$ – neglecting the prebuckling nonlinear behavior. $e = 1$, $\delta_1 = 1$, $\delta_2 = 0$ for buckling state and $e = 1$, $\delta_1 = 0$, $\delta_2 = 1$ for full nonlinear behavior. $\eta = 1$ accounts for the nonlinear terms. It should be emphasized that the present procedure, for buckling state, is based on a linear prebuckling behavior, which yields an eigenproblem.

The expressions $A_i(m,p)$, $B_i(m,p)$ and $AN_i(m,n,p)$ are given in Appendix A. Actually, these Galerkin coefficients express the equivalent values of the double and triple Fourier series. A special symbolic program using the REDUCE Compiler (Ref [18]) was written for constructing the tables for $A_i(m,p)$, $B_i(m,p)$ and $AN_i(m,n,p)$. The boundary conditions of SS_i , CC_i and FF_i were derived in the same manner and are expressed as function of the meridional coordinate only (for more details, see Ref [19]). By increasing the number of dependent variables from two (w and f) to four (w, ϕ, f and φ) where

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi &= w_{,xx} & (23) \\
\varphi &= f_{,xx}
\end{aligned}$$

the sequence is reduced to second order and the number of equations doubled. Finite difference scheme is used to reduce the ordinary differential equations to the algebraic homogeneous one for buckling type and to nonlinear system for the nonlinear behavior. Finally the Newton Raphson method is used to solve the nonlinear equations.

APPENDIX A: GALERKIN COEFFICIENTS

$$\text{Define } \frac{1}{R(\theta)} = \sum_{k=0}^{NR} \alpha_k r_k(\theta); r_k(\theta) = \cos(2k\theta)$$

and let (\cdot) denote derivative with respect to θ -coordinate.

$$\begin{aligned}
A_0(m,p) &= \oint g_m g_p d\theta \\
A_1(m,p) &= \oint \sum_k \alpha_k r_k \dot{g}_m g_p d\theta
\end{aligned}$$

$$A_2(m,p) = \oint \sum_{k_1} \sum_{k_2} \alpha_{k_1} \alpha_{k_2} [r_{k_1} \dot{r}_{k_2} \dot{g}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \ddot{g}_m] g_p d\theta$$

$$A_3(m,p) = \oint \sum_{k_1} \sum_{k_2} \sum_{k_3} \alpha_{k_1} \alpha_{k_2} \alpha_{k_3} [r_{k_1} \dot{r}_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \dot{g}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \ddot{r}_{k_3} \dot{g}_m + 3r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \ddot{g}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} r_{k_3} \ddot{\ddot{g}}_m] g_p d\theta$$

$$A_4(m,p) = \oint \sum_{k_1} \sum_{k_2} \sum_{k_3} \sum_{k_4} \alpha_{k_1} \alpha_{k_2} \alpha_{k_3} \alpha_{k_4} [r_{k_1} \dot{r}_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \dot{r}_{k_4} \dot{g}_m + 4r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \ddot{r}_{k_4} \dot{g}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} r_{k_3} \ddot{\ddot{r}}_{k_4} \dot{g}_m + 7r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \dot{r}_{k_4} \ddot{g}_m + 4r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \dot{r}_{k_3} \ddot{r}_{k_4} \ddot{g}_m + 6r_{k_1} r_{k_2} r_{k_3} \dot{r}_{k_4} \ddot{\ddot{g}}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} r_{k_3} r_{k_4} \ddot{\ddot{\ddot{g}}}_m] g_p d\theta$$

$$B_1(m,p) = \oint \sum_k \alpha_k r_k g_m g_p d\theta$$

$$AN_1(m,n,p) = \oint \sum_{k_1 k_2} \alpha_{k_1} \alpha_{k_2} [r_{k_1} \dot{r}_{k_2} \dot{g}_m + r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \ddot{g}_m] g_n g_p d\theta$$

$$AN_2(m,n,p) = \oint \sum_{k_1 k_2} \alpha_{k_1} \alpha_{k_2} r_{k_1} r_{k_2} \dot{g}_m \dot{g}_n g_p d\theta$$

Table 1. Nondimensional Fourier expansion of curvature ($R_0/R(\theta)$) for elliptic and oval cross-sections.

Eccentricity	Major axis 2A	Minor axis 2B	Ellipse	Oval
Small $\xi = 0.1$	2.064	1.932	$0.99332 + 0.1111 \cos 2\theta + 0.00151 \cos 4\theta$	$1 + 0.1 \cos 2\theta$
Medium $\xi = 0.5$	2.298	1.636	$0.92058 + 0.67345 \cos 2\theta + 0.10862 \cos 4\theta + 0.01291 \cos 6\theta + 0.00148 \cos 8\theta$	$1 + 0.5 \cos 2\theta$
Large $\xi = 1.0$	2.516	1.22	$1.0264 + 1.41091 \cos 2\theta + 0.60735 \cos 4\theta + 0.22113 \cos 6\theta + 0.07684 \cos 8\theta + 0.02581 \cos 10\theta$	$1 + \cos 2\theta$

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Figure 1: Geometry and sign convention for coordinates and displacements.

Figure 2: Curvature of elliptic and oval cross-section in terms of Fourier coefficients. a) $B/A = 0.711$, $\xi = 0.5$; b) $B/A = 0.485$, $\xi = 1.0$.